

Multi-stimuli multi-responsive fully supramolecular orthogonally bound polymer networks

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ABSTRACT

Their dynamic and stimuli-responsive nature makes supramolecular bonds useful for the design of functional polymers with adaptable properties. The combination of multiple types of supramolecular interactions in one material permits, in principle, access to multi-stimuli, multi-responsive polymers, but examples of solid materials in which different supramolecular interactions have led to useful orthogonal responses towards different stimuli are rare. Here we report a new materials platform that involves two orthogonally bound supramolecular networks. The network components are based on a trifunctional poly(propylene oxide) that was terminated with either 2,6-bis(1'-methylbenzimidazolyl)pyridine (Mebip) ligands or 2-ureido-4[1H]-pyrimidinone (UPy) groups. Supramolecular cross-linking was achieved by complexing the Mebip motifs to Zn^{2+} ions and UPy dimerization via hydrogen bonding, respectively. Orthogonal binding of the metal-ligand complex and the hydrogen bonding motifs was confirmed via spectroscopically monitored titrations. Dynamic mechanical analyses and small-angle X-ray scattering data reveal that the properties of the supramolecular networks are governed by the microphase segregation of the binding motifs into two well-defined hard phases. The ability to independently disassemble the metal-ligand complexes and UPy dimers by chemical and thermal stimuli was exploited to access double and triple shape-memory and selective healing behaviors.

INTRODUCTION

Supramolecular polymers (SPs) are assembled from monomers that form non-covalent dynamic bonds such as hydrogen bonds and metal-ligand or host-guest complexes.^{1,2} The dynamic nature of these bonds can be exploited to reversibly disassemble SPs into the constituting monomeric species, for example upon exposure to heat or light,^{3,4} chemicals that act as competitive binders,⁵ or application of a mechanical force.⁶ While the original idea associated with this approach has been to ease the processing and impart recyclability,⁷⁻¹⁰ the framework has become widely used to access a diverse set of stimuli-responsive polymers,^{11,12} such as thermally or optically healable polymers,^{3,13} mechanochromic materials,⁶ shape-memory polymers,¹⁴ and other functional materials.¹² While the vast majority of stimuli-responsive SPs contain only one single type of supramolecular motif, the combination of multiple types of supramolecular motifs, which exhibit orthogonal binding and can be addressed by different stimuli, would permit, at least in principle, access to multi-stimuli, multi-responsive polymers. However, most studies involving such materials were limited to the investigation of solvent-based systems,¹⁵ whereas examples of solid polymers in which different supramolecular interactions have led to useful orthogonal responses are rare.¹⁶ One prominent approach to such materials involves the combination of hydrogen bonding and metal-ligand motifs, which display distinct binding behavior and stimuli-responsiveness and whose properties have been extensively studied in solution.^{17,18} Some of us recently reported the preparation of blends of two supramolecular polymers based on the assembly of poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB) telechelics that were terminated with either hydrogen-bonding 2-ureido-4[1H]-pyrimidone (UPy) groups or (2,6-bis(1'-methylbenzimidazolyl)pyridine (Mebip) ligands.¹⁹ These building blocks assemble in an orthogonal manner via self-complementary hydrogen bonding (UPy-UPy) and metal-ligand complexation ($[M(\text{Mebip})_2]^{2+}$, M

= Zn, Fe), respectively. While the UPy and $[M(\text{Mebip})_2]^{2+}$ motifs could be selectively disassembled via exposure to heat or a competitive ligand, this orthogonal responsiveness could so far not be harnessed to create multi-responsive behavior. Here, we show that several intriguing response functions can be achieved by exploiting the same binding motifs in orthogonally bound supramolecular polymer networks, which represent a hitherto unexplored family of materials. The network components used are based on a trifunctional poly(propylene oxide) (PPO) core having a low glass transition temperature, which was terminated with either Mebip ligands or UPy. The common PPO core ensures the miscibility of the two star-shaped building blocks, which in the solid state assemble into supramolecular polymer networks via UPy dimerization and complexation to added Zn^{2+} ions. The binding motifs separate from the soft PPO phase into two well-defined hard phases, which can be independently and reversibly disassembled by chemical and thermal stimuli. This feature was exploited to access double and triple shape-memory behavior. We also demonstrate the possibility of healing the two supramolecular networks sequentially, which enables healing such materials under applied load.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Expanding on similar experiments with linear supramolecular polymers,¹⁹ and after confirming the orthogonality of $\text{Zn}(\text{Mebip})_2$ complexation and UPy dimerization by means of a UV-Vis titration methodology using appropriate model compounds (Supporting Figure S1 and Supporting Discussion). The results confirmed that, at least in dilute solution, these motifs have orthogonal binding characteristics. Two supramolecular macromonomers were thus synthesized by end-functionalization of a low-molecular weight star-shaped poly(propylene oxide) (PPO) triamine with a number-average molecular weight (M_n) of 5000 g/mol with either UPy (**M1**) or

Figure 1. Synthesis of macromonomers via the functionalization of the amine end-groups of a PPO core with i) UPy units (**M1**), which dimerizes to form a hydrogen-bonded supramolecular network, and ii) Mebip ligands (**M2**), which were coordinated to $Zn(NTf_2)_2$ and form a metallosupramolecular network (**M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**). The figure also shows a representation of the supramolecular networks **M1-M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** displaying binding motifs with orthogonal response to a chemical or heat. The NTf_2^- counterions are omitted for clarity.

MeBip (**M2**) units (Figure 1). The choice of PPO as backbone was based on its low glass transition temperature (T_g) of $-58\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (determined for the PPO triamine by DSC) and relatively low

polarity, which were expected to promote nanophase-segregation of the supramolecular motifs into discrete hard phases.²⁰ The PPO triamine was reacted with an excess (1.5 eq. per amine) of 2-(6-isocyanatohexylaminocarbonylamino)-6-methyl-4[1H]pyrimidinone to yield the UPy-functionalized building block **M1** or an excess (3.3 eq. per amine) of 2,2'-(4-((6-bromohexyl)oxy)pyridine-2,6-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole) to prepare the Mebip-terminated **M2** (Figure 1). The amine end-group conversion was complete in both cases, as confirmed by ¹⁹F-NMR-based titration (Supporting Figure S18) according to the method reported by Macosko *et al.*²¹ While **M1** features three UPy groups, we elected to terminate **M2** with six Mebip end-groups, as secondary amination proved difficult to avoid and efforts to create the trifunctional compound yielded mixed products. MALDI-TOF spectroscopy was used to determine the molecular weight of macromonomers **M1** ($M_n = 5700$ g/mol) and **M2** ($M_n = 7100$ g/mol), which matched the values established by ¹H NMR end-group analysis (5600 g/mol) and in the case of **M2** also UV-Vis titrations with Zn(NTf₂)₂ (7100 g/mol, *vide infra*).

With the two macromonomers in hand, we first confirmed that the orthogonal binding observed for the model compounds (*vide supra*) is retained in **M1** and **M2**, using UV-Vis titrations, i.e., the same methodology as applied for the model compounds (Supporting Figures S2-S4). The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of **M2** shows an absorbance band associated with the free ligand at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 310$ nm (Supporting Figure S2). Upon adding Zn(NTf₂)₂, the expected band with λ_{max} at 354 nm appears and a decrease of the ligand's absorbance is observed. A plot of the absorbance at 354 nm against the Zn²⁺:**M2** ratio shows an increase of the absorbance up to the stoichiometric point (i.e., at a Zn²⁺:**M2** ratio of 3:1, Supporting Figure S4), and no additional changes are seen upon further increasing the Zn(NTf₂)₂ content. The titration of a mixture of **M1** and **M2** with a stoichiometric equivalent of Zn(NTf₂)₂ showed no interference of **M1** in the

formation of the metal complex (Supporting Figures S3 and S4), confirming the orthogonality of the two supramolecular interactions (also) when attached to a polymer structure.

M1, **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** and blends of these supramolecular polymer networks ((**M1**)_x-(**M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**)₁ where $x = 1$ or 2) were processed into robust, self-supporting films with a thickness of ~ 200 - $250 \mu\text{m}$ by solvent casting from a 9:1 v/v CHCl₃/CH₃CN mixture and subsequent compression molding at 90 °C or 100 °C. For reference purposes, a covalently cross-linked polyether network (**C1**) was synthesized via the aza-Michael reaction of the PPO triamine with 1,6-hexanediol diacrylate (Supporting Figure S5).

Figure 2. SAXS spectra of the covalent reference material **C1**, the individual supramolecular polymers **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** and mixtures of **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**. Spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

To probe the morphology of these materials, small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments were conducted (Figure 2, Supporting Table S1). The SAXS pattern of the hydrogen-bonded net-

work formed by **M1** (orange trace) shows a single broad diffraction peak, indicative of a phase segregated structure with a characteristic length of 7.9 nm. The SAXS spectrum of the metallosupramolecular network **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** (blue trace) exhibits equidistant Bragg diffraction peaks up to the second order, in agreement with a lamellar morphology in which the distance between metal-ligand aggregates is 8.5 nm. Thus, both homopolymers adopt phase-segregated morphologies in which hard phases formed by UPy dimers and [Zn(Mebip)₂](NTf₂)₂ complexes, respectively, serve to physically cross-link the low-*T_g* PPO phase, similar to previously investigated linear supramolecular polymers featuring a hydrocarbon core and the two binding motifs.^{14,22} The SAXS patterns of blends of the two components (**M1**)₂-(**M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**)₁ (black trace) and (**M1**)₁-(**M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**)₁ (green trace) appear as superpositions of those of the individual networks **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**, pointing to an unchanged, lamellar morphology, whereas the reference network **C1** (magenta trace) shows a broad peak around 7.0 nm which, according to the literature, is ascribed to some phase separation of the hydrogen-bonding domains (β-aminoesters) and the PPO domains.²³

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA) were used to investigate the thermal and thermomechanical properties of the as-processed individual supramolecular polymers and their blends (Figure 3,

Table 1). The DSC traces of all samples show a glass transition of the PPO phase at ca. -58 °C and endotherms at 50-60 °C, which are indicative of the evaporation of a small fraction of adsorbed water (Figure 3a). The DSC spectrum of the covalent reference network also displays an endothermic transition at 190 °C, which is attributed to the decomposition of the network via a retro aza-Michael addition (Supporting Figure S5).²⁴ The traces of the neat **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** supramolecular networks show endothermic peaks at ca. 110 °C and 240 °C,

respectively, associated with melting/dissociation of hard phases formed by the respective supramolecular motifs. Indeed, both materials were observed to undergo a solid-to-viscous-fluid transition at these temperatures. The thermogram of $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ is a linear combination of the traces of the two homopolymers, suggesting the coexistence of two orthogonally built hard phases. The DSC trace of $((\mathbf{M1})_1-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1)$ does not show the transition associated with the UPy stacks, suggesting that the formation of the UPy hard phase is suppressed if the fraction of $\mathbf{M1}$ is reduced beyond a threshold. Figure 3b shows the DMA traces of the supramolecular networks and the covalent reference network. The curves reflect high storage moduli (E') between 1.8 and 3.0 GPa below $-58\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, consistent with the glassy nature of the PPO phase at this temperature. Above the PPO T_g , $\mathbf{C1}$ is a very soft rubber, with a very low room temperature modulus (0.17 MPa) and a failure temperature of ca. $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, arguably due to retro-Michael driven decomposition (*vide supra*).

Figure 3. (a) Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) traces (1st heating, $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) and (b) dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA, $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) traces of the covalent reference network $\mathbf{C1}$, the individual supramolecular networks $\mathbf{M1}$ and $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ and mixtures of $\mathbf{M1}$ and $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the covalent reference network **C1**, the individual supramolecular networks **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** and mixtures of **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**.^a

Sample	E' at -70 °C (MPa) ^b	E' at 25 °C (MPa) ^b	E' at 130 °C (MPa) ^b	Failure temperature (°C) ^b	Young's Modulus (MPa) ^c	Tensile strength (MPa) ^c	Strain at break (%) ^c
C1	1355 ± 342	0.17 ± 0.03	0.13 ± 0.05	160-170	0.10 ± 0.05	0.069 ± 0.004	128 ± 8
M1	2824 ± 340	13.5 ± 2.9	-	110-120	13.6 ± 1.4	0.7 ± 0.02	6.4 ± 0.6
M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂	3154 ± 164	53.7 ± 9.4	17.8 ± 7.4	220-240	29.0 ± 4.2	2.7 ± 0.1	83.6 ± 1.5
(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁	3109 ± 509	31.3 ± 1.5	0.41 ± 0.11	195-205	17.5 ± 1.4	1.1 ± 0.1	15.3 ± 3.4
(M1)₁-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁	2615 ± 428	13.4 ± 0.8	2.6 ± 0.6	205-210	5.9 ± 1.3	0.49 ± 0.03	20.1 ± 2.0

^aData represent averages of $n = 3-7$ individual measurements ± standard deviation. ^bMeasured by DMA. ^cMeasured by stress-strain experiments at 25 °C with a strain rate of 5 %/min.

The DMA traces of the supramolecular homopolymer networks are qualitatively similar, but the rubbery plateaus are characterized by higher moduli (**M1** = 13.5 MPa, **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** = 53.7 MPa, both quoted for 25 °C) and the failure temperatures (ca. 115 and 230 °C) correspond to the melting/transition temperatures of the hard phases as observed by DSC (Figure 3a). The presence of a rubbery plateau in both these materials is in good agreement with the presence of a crystalline hard phase (*vide supra*), which physically cross-links the PPO matrix and makes them stable at ambient conditions. The significantly higher E' of **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** is consistent with its substantially higher binding motif content. Gratifyingly, the DMA trace of the **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** blend is a combination of the traces of the parent homopolymers, and shows two well-defined rubbery plateaus (with $E' = 31.3$ and 0.4 MPa) and sharp modulus drops at ca. 115 and 200 °C, matching again the transitions observed by DSC. Consistent with the lower **M1** content and the absence of a UPy hard phase (*vide supra*) the **(M1)₁-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** blend features a lower E' than **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** below the melting temperature of the UPy

stacks in the latter, no sharp modulus drop around this temperature, and a higher E' in the temperature rubbery regime, where the $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ content is the main load-bearing component. Altogether, the DSC and DMA data confirm the orthogonality of the supramolecular binding motifs and the possibility of addressing them selectively by heating the materials above the respective transition temperature.

The mechanical properties of the various materials were further probed by tensile tests that were conducted at room temperature (Figure 4,

Table 1). The reference polymer **C1** shows the typical stress-strain curve of a weakly cross-linked elastomer, with a Young's modulus of 0.1 MPa, a tensile strength of 0.07 MPa, and an elongation at break of 128%. The supramolecular networks **M1** and $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ show a substantially higher stiffness (Young's moduli = 13.6 MPa and 29.0 MPa) and tensile strength (0.7 and 2.7 MPa), whereas the elongation at break is reduced to 6.4% in **M1** and 83.6 % in $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$. These characteristics are related to the hard phase in the supramolecular networks, which, as also reflected by the DMA data, is more pronounced in the metallosupramolecular polymer. The significantly higher elongation at break in the latter is arguably due to two factors, namely i) the higher binding constant of the metal complex, which yields higher apparent molecular weights that result in a more entangled network, and ii) the fact that **M2** has six Mebip units, which leads to a network with a higher cross-linking degree. The tensile properties of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ fall between those of the individual polymer networks (Young's modulus of 17.5 MPa, tensile strength of 1.1 MPa and an elongation at break of 15.3%). By contrast, the $(\mathbf{M1})_1\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ blend has a lower modulus (5.9 MPa) and strength (0.49 MPa) than all other supramolecular polymer compositions investigated, which is

consistent with the interpretation that the crystallization of the UPy dimers is largely prevented in this sample (*vide supra*).

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of films of the covalent reference network **C1**, the individual supramolecular networks **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** and mixtures of **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂**.

The data presented above support the conclusion that **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** is indeed a nanophase segregated supramolecular network with two distinct, orthogonally addressable hard phases. The ability to independently disassemble the UPy dimers and metal-ligand complexes and utilize these phases as either network points or switches was exploited to enable double and triple shape-memory effects. In a first experiment, the melting of the UPy phase was used as the switch and the Mebip-Zn²⁺ hard phase served to maintain a permanent network. Figure 5 shows pictures of qualitative experiments, in which a film of **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** was heated to 110 °C (i.e. above the T_m of the UPy hard phase), formed into a coil while hot, and cooled to ambient while held into place, to fix a temporary shape. This resulted in excellent shape retention, while

the sample quickly recovered its initial shape (2 sec) when heated to 110 °C (Figure 5 and Supporting Video V1).

The thermally-induced shape-memory properties of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ were quantitatively evaluated in a cyclic DMA equipment. Figure 6 shows a two-dimensional graph that depicts the change of strain, stress and temperature of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ over multiple cycles. In brief, the sample was heated to 110 °C and then strained with a force of 0.005 N. The temporary shape was fixed by cooling the sample to 25 °C and the applied stress was subsequently removed. The initial shape was recovered by heating the sample to 110 °C and cooling back to 25 °C to recover the remaining strain that results from the thermal expansion. The fixity and recovery ratio were calculated as shown in the Supporting Information. The analysis of the data shows an excellent fixity for all three cycles (99 ± 0.1 , 99 ± 0.2 , and $99 \pm 0.2\%$, respectively), and a recovery ratio of $48 \pm 4.1\%$ for the first cycle and 77 ± 2.3 and $87 \pm 3.9\%$ for the following cycles. The difference in strain-recovery ratio between the first and the following cycles may be attributed to residual strain resulting from the processing history of the sample²⁵ or result from some rearrangement of the supramolecular hard phase.

Figure 5. Pictures demonstrating the thermally triggered one-way dual-shape shape-memory behavior of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$. The film was (i) heated at 110 °C, curled and cooled to ambient temperature to fix the temporary shape and (ii) subsequently re-heated to 110 °C to recover the initial shape.

Figure 6. Thermally triggered one-way dual-shape-memory cycles of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$. The graph shows the change of strain, stress and temperature over time in force-controlled shape-memory cycles. The film was uniaxially strained at 110 °C with a set force of 0.005 N, and the temperature was reduced to 25 °C, while the force was kept constant. The load was removed and the sample was heated again to 110 °C and subsequently cooled to 25 °C to allow the material to recover its initial shape. Three consecutive cycles were conducted.

In a second shape-memory experiment, we examined the potential of using the Mebip- Zn^{2+} hard phase as chemically addressable switch, and the UPy hard phase to form the permanent network. Rowan and co-workers¹⁴ reported a chemo-responsive shape-memory material containing a Mebip- Eu^{2+} hard phase, which could be plasticized using solvents such as methanol or acetone. In the present system, these solvents could also influence the UPy hard phase and were thus replaced with the possibly more selective tetramethylethylenediamine (TMEDA), an amine-based ligand that acts as a competitive binder for Zn^{2+} .¹⁹

Figure 7. Selectivity of TMEDA towards the metal complex. (a) Representative DMA traces of films of supramolecular networks **M1** and $(\text{M1})_2-(\text{M2}\cdot\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2)$ before and after exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min. (b) Optical micrographs of a $\text{M2}\cdot\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$ film between crossed polarizers, half protected by a glass cover (as indicated with red rectangles), before and after being exposed to TMEDA vapors (scale bar = $100\ \mu\text{m}$). (c) Comparison of the UV-Vis absorption spectra of a $\text{M2}\cdot\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$ film ($10\ \mu\text{m}$) on a quartz substrate before and after exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min. (d) Plot of the ratio of the absorbance recorded at 340 and 310 nm (corresponding to the absorption maxima of the Mebip- Zn^{2+} complex and the free Mebip

ligand) of $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ films ($<10\ \mu\text{m}$) as a function of time exposed to TMEDA vapors; data represent averages of three samples and the error bars represent the standard deviation.

The advantage of TMEDA over other more typical ligands such as *N, N, N', N'', N'''*-pentane-methyldiethylenetriamine (PMEDTA)¹⁹ is its low boiling point, which facilitates its application from the gas phase and removal in vacuum. We first investigated the selectivity of TMEDA towards the metal complex by exposing films of $\mathbf{M1}$, $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ and $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ to TMEDA vapors for 3 min. $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ transformed into a viscous liquid – arguably due to the dissolution of the hard phase – and could thus not be analyzed further. Figure 7a shows a comparison of the thermo-mechanical properties of $\mathbf{M1}$ and $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ before and directly after exposure to the TMEDA vapors. The DMA traces show clearly that the TMEDA exposure does not affect the mechanical properties of $\mathbf{M1}$, suggesting that the UPy hard phase is not affected. By contrast, the DMA trace of $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ shows a lower storage modulus after TMEDA exposure suggesting that the Mebip- Zn^{2+} hard phase is (at least partially) affected.

To further explore the binding with TMEDA, we examined the UV–Vis absorption spectrum of a dilute $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ solution ($6.6\ \mu\text{M}$) of $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ upon addition of TMEDA. Interestingly, the results show that the Mebip- Zn^{2+} complex is only fully dissociated in the presence of a large excess ($40'000\ \text{eq.}$) of TMEDA (Supporting Figure S6). Indeed, a comparison of the UV-Vis absorption spectra of a $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ film before and after exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min (Figure 7c) and a plot of the ratio of the absorbance recorded at 340 and 310 nm (corresponding to the absorption maxima of the Mebip- Zn^{2+} complex and the free Mebip ligand) of $\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2$ films as a function of time exposed to TMEDA vapors (Figure 7d) show that the Mebip- Zn^{2+} complex does not fully dissociate. This result supports the

conclusion that the Mebip-Zn²⁺ complexes in **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** dissociate partially upon exposure to TMEDA vapors (as shown in the graphic of Figure 1), and that the modulus drop observed by DMA is due to TMEDA acting on the Mebip-Zn²⁺ hard phase. Further proof that TMEDA acts on the Mebip-Zn²⁺ hard phase was obtained by analyzing a film of **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** before and after exposure to TMEDA by SAXS and DSC (Supporting Figures S7 and S8). The SAXS spectrum after TMEDA exposure still shows a nanophase segregated structure, albeit with a reduced domain spacing. In addition the DSC trace after TMEDA exposure shows the melting of the UPy hard phase but lacks the endotherm associated to the melting of the Mebip-Zn²⁺ hard phase. Yet another qualitative proof was obtained by monitoring a film of **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** by cross-polarized optical microscopy before and after exposure to TMEDA vapors (Figure 7b). The images show that in the exposed portions of the film the pronounced birefringence disappeared rapidly and the solid transformed into a viscous liquid. Thus these results suggest that TMEDA appears to primarily act by dissolving the metal-ligand hard phase, whereas the effect on the Mebip-Zn²⁺ complex dissociation appears to be minor.

To demonstrate that the disassembly of the Mebip-Zn²⁺ hard phase can be used as the switching element for a shape memory effect, a rectangular film of IPN **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** was exposed to TMEDA vapors for 3 minutes, bent, and placed under vacuum for 12 h to completely remove TMEDA and fix the temporary shape (Figure 8a). The film was then re-exposed to TMEDA vapors and recovered its initial shape in 3 min (Figure 8a and Supporting Video V2). With these results in hand, we sought to address the two hard phases sequentially to access a triple-shape-memory effect. Thus, a film of IPN **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** was i) exposed to TMEDA vapors, ii) bent at an angle of 90 °, iii) placed under vacuum to remove TMEDA and fix the 1st temporary shape, iv) heated to 110 °C, v) bent further into an S-shape, and vi) cooled

to ambient to fix the 2nd temporary shape (Figure 8b). Figure 8b demonstrates that the IPN indeed permits fixing both the 1st and the 2nd temporary shape with good fidelity and re-heating to 110 °C and re-exposure to TMEDA vapors lead to restoration of the 1st temporary and the permanent shape, respectively. Based on the data shown in Figure 7, which unequivocally reveal that the UPy motifs completely dissociate at the programming temperature of 110 °C, whereas only a fraction of the Mebip/Zn²⁺ complexes is disrupted by TMEDA, we conclude that the remaining metallosupramolecular polymer network defines and promotes the restoration of the initial shape.

Figure 8. (a) Pictures demonstrating the chemically triggered one-way dual-shape shape-memory behavior of a film of IPN $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$. The initial film was (i) exposed to TMEDA vapors for 3 min, deformed and placed in vacuum and (ii) re-exposed to TMEDA to recover the initial shape in 3 min. (b) Pictures demonstrating the chemically and thermally-triggered triple shape-memory behavior of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$. The film was (i) exposed to TMEDA vapors for 3 min, bent and dried under vacuum, (ii) heated at 110 °C, bent into an S-shape and cooled to room temperature, (iii) re-heated to 110 °C to recover the 1st temporary shape and (iv) re-exposed to TMEDA vapors to recover the initial shape.

The temporary dissociation of supramolecular polymers and the concomitant viscosity decrease a priori allows for the repair of damages or defects.^{3,26} To this end, we investigated the stimuli-driven healing properties of the IPN by intentionally damaging films of **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** under well-controlled conditions, i.e. by scratching their surface with a razor blade to a depth of ~50-70% of the film thickness (Figure 9a). In a first experiment, half of the films were exposed to TMEDA vapors for 3 min while the other half was heated to 150 °C for 5 min. These treatments led to partial disappearance of the cuts in both series (Figure 9a), which suggests that in each case only one network was healed. The experiment was repeated, but the films were now first exposed to TMEDA vapors and subsequently heated to 150 °C. This treatment resulted in the almost complete disappearance of the cut, confirming our initial speculation that two orthogonally bound IPNs can be healed sequentially (Figure 9a). In control experiments, **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** films were exposed to TMEDA vapors and heated, respectively, and as expected, the optical micrographs showed no significant changes (Supporting Figure S9). The healing imparted by the various treatments was further quantified by means of tensile tests using previously damaged films of **(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁** (Supporting Table S2). Figure 9b shows the stress-strain curves of the original, damaged and healed samples. The data show that the scratches reduce the strain at break to half and the toughness (determined from the area under the stress-strain curve) from $124 \pm 17 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ to $36 \pm 6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The application of one stimulus (as described above) somewhat increased both the strain at break and the toughness (Figure 9b and Figure 9c). The healing efficiencies of the chemically and the thermally healed samples were $64 \pm 12 \%$ and $53 \pm 14 \%$, respectively (Figure 9d). When the damage film was exposed to both stimuli sequentially, the original strain at break and toughness were fully recovered (healing efficiency of $102 \pm 39 \%$). It is noted that both temperature and TMEDA

did not cause a change in the visual aspect of the samples, which further indicates that these stimuli do not lead to macrophase segregation of the two networks (Supporting Figure S10).

Figure 9. (a) Optical micrograph illustrating the selective healing of one network (chemically or thermally induced) and the healing of both networks (chemically and thermally induced) on a scratched film of $(M1)_2-(M2 \cdot Zn(NTf_2)_2)_1$ (scale bar = 200 μm). (b) Stress-strain curves of films of IPN $(M1)_2-(M2 \cdot Zn(NTf_2)_2)_1$; shown are data for the original (grey) and damaged (blue), as well as samples that were healed by TMEDA vapors (green), healed by heat (red), or healed using both stimuli (orange). (c) Toughness of films of IPN $(M1)_2-(M2 \cdot Zn(NTf_2)_2)_1$ determined by the

area below the stress-strain curves (error bars represent the standard deviation). (d) Healing efficiency of films of IPN $(\mathbf{M1})_2\text{-}(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ (error bars represent the standard deviation).

CONCLUSIONS

The reported supramolecular polymer system based on two orthogonally bound supramolecular networks is the first representative of a hitherto unexplored family of materials. The solid-state properties of the materials are dictated by the phase segregation of the binding motifs into well-defined hard phases, which can be selectively and reversibly addressed by thermal and other stimuli. This was exploited to access double and triple shape-memory and selective healing behaviors. One can reasonably expect that the findings reported are applicable to other binding motif combinations and that they allow imparting other functionalities.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Experimental methods, synthetic procedures, supporting discussion, and additional characterization. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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REFERENCES

- (1) Brunsveld, L.; Folmer, B. J. B.; Meijer, E. W.; Sijbesma, R. P. Supramolecular Polymers. *Chem. Rev.* **2001**, *101*, 4071-4098.
- (2) Yang, L.; Tan, X.; Wang, Z.; Zhang, X. Supramolecular Polymers: Historical Development, Preparation, Characterization, and Functions. *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 7196-7239.
- (3) Burnworth, M.; Tang, L.; Kumpfer, J. R.; Duncan, A. J.; Beyer, F. L.; Fiore, G. L.; Rowan, S. J.; Weder, C. Optically healable supramolecular polymers. *Nature* **2011**, *472*, 334-337.
- (4) Heinzmann, C.; Coulibaly, S.; Roulin, A.; Fiore, G. L.; Weder, C. Light-induced bonding and debonding with supramolecular adhesives. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2014**, *6*, 4713-4719.
- (5) Yan, X. Z.; Xu, D. H.; Chi, X. D.; Chen, J. Z.; Dong, S. Y.; Ding, X.; Yu, Y. H.; Huang, F. H. A Multiresponsive, Shape-Persistent, and Elastic Supramolecular Polymer Network Gel Constructed by Orthogonal Self-Assembly. *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 362-369.
- (6) Balkenende, D. W. R.; Coulibaly, S.; Balog, S.; Simon, Y. C.; Fiore, G. L.; Weder, C. Mechanochemistry with Metallosupramolecular Polymers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 10493-10498.

- (7) Sijbesma, R. P.; Beijer, F. H.; Brunsveld, L.; Folmer, B. J. B.; Hirschberg, J. H. K. K.; Lange, R. F. M.; Lowe, J. K. L.; Meijer, E. W. Reversible Polymers Formed from Self-Complementary Monomers Using Quadruple Hydrogen Bonding. *Science* **1997**, *278*, 1601-1604.
- (8) Sivakova, S.; Bohnsack, D. A.; Mackay, M. E.; Suwanmala, P.; Rowan, S. J. Utilization of a Combination of Weak Hydrogen-Bonding Interactions and Phase Segregation to Yield Highly Thermosensitive Supramolecular Polymers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, *127*, 18202-18211.
- (9) Chino, K.; Ashiura, M. Thermoreversible Cross-Linking Rubber Using Supramolecular Hydrogen-Bonding Networks. *Macromolecules* **2001**, *34*, 9201-9204.
- (10) Van Gemert, G. M. L.; Janssen, H. M.; Meijer, E. W.; Bosman, A. W. Supramolecular polymers from low-melting, easily processable building blocks. US 20100076147 A1, Mars 25, 2010.
- (11) Wojtecki, R. J.; Meador, M. A.; Rowan, S. J. Using the dynamic bond to access macroscopically responsive structurally dynamic polymers. *Nat Mater* **2011**, *10*, 14-27.
- (12) Yan, X.; Wang, F.; Zheng, B.; Huang, F. Stimuli-responsive supramolecular polymeric materials. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 6042-6065.
- (13) Balkenende, D. W. R.; Monnier, C. A.; Fiore, G. L.; Weder, C. Optically responsive supramolecular polymer glasses. *Nat Commun* **2016**, *7*, 10995.
- (14) Kumpfer, J. R.; Rowan, S. J. Thermo-, photo-, and chemo-responsive shape-memory properties from photo-cross-linked metallo-supramolecular polymers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 12866-12874.

- (15) Li, S.-L.; Xiao, T.; Lin, C.; Wang, L. Advanced supramolecular polymers constructed by orthogonal self-assembly. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 5950-5968.
- (16) Herbert, K. M.; Schrettl, S.; Rowan, S. J.; Weder, C. 50th Anniversary Perspective: Solid-State Multistimuli, Multiresponsive Polymeric Materials. *Macromolecules* **2017**, *50*, 8845-8870.
- (17) Hofmeier, H.; Schubert, U. S. Combination of orthogonal supramolecular interactions in polymeric architectures. *Chem. Commun.* **2005**, 2423-2432.
- (18) Elacqua, E.; Lye, D. S.; Weck, M. Engineering Orthogonality in Supramolecular Polymers: From Simple Scaffolds to Complex Materials. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *47*, 2405-2416.
- (19) Coulibaly, S.; Heinzmann, C.; Beyer, F. L.; Balog, S.; Weder, C.; Fiore, G. L. Supramolecular Polymers with Orthogonal Functionality. *Macromolecules* **2014**, *47*, 8487-8496.
- (20) Cortese, J.; Soulie-Ziakovic, C.; Cloitre, M.; Tence-Girault, S.; Leibler, L. Order-disorder transition in supramolecular polymers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 19672-19675.
- (21) Ji, S.; Hoye, T. R.; Macosko, C. W. Primary Amine (–NH₂) Quantification in Polymers: Functionality by ¹⁹F NMR Spectroscopy. *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 4679-4686.
- (22) Kautz, H.; van Beek, D. J. M.; Sijbesma, R. P.; Meijer, E. W. Cooperative End-to-End and Lateral Hydrogen-Bonding Motifs in Supramolecular Thermoplastic Elastomers. *Macromolecules* **2006**, *39*, 4265-4267.
- (23) Sánchez-Ferrer, A.; Rogez, D.; Martinoty, P. Synthesis and Characterization of New Polyurea Elastomers by Sol/Gel Chemistry. *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *211*, 1712-1721.

(24) Baruah, R.; Kumar, A.; Ujjwal, R. R.; Kedia, S.; Ranjan, A.; Ojha, U. Recyclable Thermosets Based on Dynamic Amidation and Aza-Michael Addition Chemistry. *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49*, 7814-7824.

(25) Xiao, X. L.; Kong, D. Y.; Qiu, X. Y.; Zhang, W. B.; Liu, Y. J.; Zhang, S.; Zhang, F. H.; Hu, Y.; Leng, J. S. Shape memory polymers with high and low temperature resistant properties. *Sci Rep-Uk* **2015**, *5*, 14137.

(26) Bosman, A. W.; Sijbesma, R. P.; Meijer, E. W. Supramolecular polymers at work. *Mater. Today* **2004**, *7*, 34-39.

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